

NOTES

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	Colour	%Cd		%Sulphur		ΔM mhos cm^{-2}	$\nu(C-S)$	$\nu(C=S)$	$\nu(C-N)$	$\nu(M-N)$	$\nu(M-S)$
		Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.						
P-dtc	White	—	—	—	—	—	890	1260	1430	—	—
M-dtc	do	—	—	—	—	—	895	1250	1425	—	—
Cd(P-dtc) ₂	White amorphous	25.67	25.99	29.42	29.60	6.5	875	1220	1435	350	260
Cd(P-dtc) ₂ Py	Brown, crystalline	21.42	21.76	24.29	24.78	10.0	885	1225	1440	360	250
Cd(P-dtc) ₂ β -pic	White do	20.75	21.19	23.80	24.18	12.8	890	1230	1440	345	260
Cd(P-dtc) ₂ γ -pic	Brownish white crystalline	20.86	21.19	23.95	24.13	7.5	875	1230	1450	350	260
Cd(P-dtc) ₂ IQ	do	19.76	20.02	22.48	22.79	14.0	880	1225	1445	350	255
Cd(M-dtc) ₂	White amorphous	25.48	25.75	29.08	29.33	7.0	885	1240	1420	355	250
Cd(M-dtc) ₂ β -pic	Brown, crystalline	20.87	21.03	23.52	23.95	8.7	890	1250	1430	345	260
Cd(M-dtc) ₂ γ -pic	do	20.72	21.03	23.65	23.95	8.9	890	1260	1425	350	260
Cd(M-dtc) ₂ -pip	do	21.28	21.55	24.18	24.54	12.5	895	1250	1425	350	255

P-dtc=piperidyl dithiocarbamate, M-dtc=Morpholyl dithiocarbamate, Py=Pyridine, β -pic= β -Picoline, γ -Pic= γ -Picoline, IQ=Isoquinoline, Pip=Piperidine.

low melting points and low conductance values in acetone, ΔM lying in the range of 6.5-14.0 mhos cm^{-2} indicating non-electrolytic nature of these complexes.

Ir spectra of dithiocarbamates have been studied earlier by Nakamoto *et al.*⁶. Some of the absorption bands and the base adducts have been assigned. The appearance of the bands around 890 and $\sim 1260\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free ligands can be assigned as thiol (C-S) and thiocarbonyl (C=S) absorption bands respectively. Shifting of these bands to lower frequencies in case of metal chelates indicates the bonding of both the sulphur atoms to the metal ion. In base-adducts these bands are again shifted to higher frequency region due to the interaction of σ -bonding nitrogen ligands. In addition, most of the free nitrogen ligand absorption bands are modified in the complexes indicating bonding to the metal ion. Furthermore, the conclusive evidence of bonding is proved by the occurrence⁸ of $\nu(M-N)$ and $\nu(M-S)$ around 350 cm^{-1} and $\sim 250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively in the far ir spectra of the complexes.

Bis(piperidyl or morpholyl dithiocarbamate) Cd(II) complexes are presumably penta-coordinated polymers as inferred from their analysis, high melting point and sparing solubility in common organic solvents. When these metal chelates are refluxed with heterocyclic nitrogen donors for about 2 hrs probably these polymers break up giving rise to pent-coordinated mono-adducts. Hence, the complexes reported in the present investigation are presumably penta-coordinated like the base adducts of β -diketonates^{7,8}, γ -substituted β -diketonates⁹⁻¹⁰ and γ -substituted β -keto arylamide¹¹. However, X-ray crystallography study will reveal the exact stereochemistry of these complexes.

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Spectrophotometric, Potentiometric and Visual Determination of Nitrate with Iron(II)

N. KRISHNAMURTY* and A. V. SURYANARAYANA
Department of Engineering Chemistry, Andhra University,
Waltair-530 003

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NITRATE is directly determined with iron(II) in 9-12 M phosphoric acid by spectrophotometric (in presence of thiocyanate), potentiometric and visual methods using azure A, azure C, methylene blue, methylene green, thionine, cacotheline and ferrion as indicators. The method is extended for the determination of nitrate in fertiliser samples which offers a simple and convenient method over the earlier methods. Potassium which is an important constituent of the fertilisers is also determined by precipitating it quantitatively with nitric acid.

Various methods available for the determination of nitrate need complicated apparatus, are time consuming and approximate. Moreover, different reagents do not react with nitrate in a simple stoichiometric way and give rise to the formation

* Dr. N. Krishnamurty, Head of the Department of Engineering Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair-530 003.